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Nurturing Love for the Homeland as a Model for Primary School Work

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Abstract

The study aims to consolidate the experience of the Department of Primary Education of Samara State University of Social Sciences and Education in nurturing the love for the homeland while creating a verified model of the educational system. It includes stimulation models of future teachers' interaction with students designated to nurture the love for the homeland recursively and accommodates regional specificities of the alumni professional activity and the employers' needs. Among study methods, we can mention exploring specialized literature for verifying the design model, handling moral development concepts, modelling the system of teachers' value-based competencies, and the glossing technique. Pedagogical modelling is a leading method. The study has been performed for three years. The study revealed a recursive nature of the design model of nurturing the love for the homeland, a professional and moral value reflected in the diffusing stimulation models of interaction between students and primary school children as innovative learning formats and pedagogical techniques. The model of nurturing the love for the homeland promotes coordination of hands-on training of future teachers in professional and moral values in various fields of study; content orthogonality of the educational design model encompassing different ways of cooperating with museums, libraries, and cultural sites outside the lecture halls; raising public resources in order to implement it, which allows the students to produce facilitating stimulation models; axiological priorities in teacher education forming a comprehensive training system and fostering continuity of core curricula at any level of education. The study validity was tested in the course of a pedagogical experiment.

Keywords: pedagogical modelling, pedagogical axiology, love for the homeland.

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Introduction

According to the Federal State Educational Standards of preschool, primary general and vocational education and professional teaching standards, nowadays, there is an urgent need to instil and cultivate professional and moral values, e.g. patriotism as an essential constituent (Maslov & Maslova, 2013), in students. It is attributable to the axiological priorities of teacher education (Slastenin & Chizhanova, 2003) in Russia. Nurturing the love for the homeland (LFHL) contributes to fostering patriotism. The educational setting of the institution is conducive to including the regional upbringing component. The factors mentioned above increase the relevance of promoting the educational setting of the institution. Its core curricula cover the system of upbringing. Modern researchers are designing the methodological foundation of modelling in pedagogical education (Kozyreva, 2010; Lodatko, 2008; Campbell, Seok, Maughn, Kiriazis, & Zuwallack, 2015; Major et al., 2020). Nevertheless, specialized literature does not duly address the issues of instilling and cultivating LFHL in students based on modelling the system of working at a pedagogical university and considering the specificities of the regional constituent.

Purpose and objectives of the study

The study has two goals: 1) creating the model of nurturing LFHL at the Department of Primary Education (DPE) of Samara State University of Social Sciences and Education (SSUSSE) based on regional specificities of the alumni professional activity and of the employers' needs; 2) exploring the issue of pedagogical modelling in specialized literature, typical challenges of fostering patriotism at university and primary school; applying the results of pedagogical modelling as tools of pedagogical education. Thus, objectives of the study can be defined as follows: modelling the areas, kinds, and ways of upbringing designated to instil LFHL in students based on pedagogical innovation theory, the experience of DPE of SSUSSE in fostering LFHL, regional specificities of the alumni professional activity and the employers' needs; allowing the students to produce a series of facilitating simulation models aimed at nurturing LFHL in primary schoolchildren; identifying the existence or non-existence of positive feedback in the design model and the model aimed at nurturing LFHL in primary schoolchildren; testing the verification of the design model via different test methods under the well-defined set of constituents and criteria.

Literature review

Nurturing LFHL in students entails modern approaches to fostering patriotism (Slepenkova & Shchetinina, 2016). Pedagogical axiology is a crucial aspect (Zhuykova, 2012; Zenkovich, 2013). Having explored the axiological constituent of the students' personalities, educators design the curricula aimed at harmonization and alignment of social values and personal beliefs (Kudinov, Kudinov, Kudinova, & Belousova, 2018).

Modern pedagogical innovation theory acknowledges modelling in upbringing and education (Ivanyan, 2013). Didactic modelling is topical (Vladimirova, 2016). Social interaction is material to upbringing. It contributes to the students' personal development, proximal development, and acquiring knowledge (Conceição & Margarida, 2014). Taking the innovative personal potential into account has relevance when the mechanisms of self-development of humans are interpreted as an open self-organizing system (Klochko & Galazhinsky, 2009).

Nurturing LFHL in multiethnic regions entails creating a multicultural educational space in the Russian Federation. It is vital nowadays (Belogurov, Voevoda, Inozemtsev, Romanova, & Khokhlova, 2020).

Methodology

The study's methodology rests on exploring philosophical, pedagogical, and methodological literature for verifying the design model; the method focusing on the concepts and values of moral development, modelling the system of teachers' value-based competencies, the glossing technique. Pedagogical modelling was a leading method. This study takes into consideration the findings of pedagogical modelling of fostering patriotism (Kuzmina, 2015) at university (Salikov, 2008) and primary school (Maslova, 2014).

Topical pedagogical studies address patriotic education globally, whereas this study focuses on nurturing LFHL, as the most verifiable constituent of studies. "Love for the motherland is impossible without LFHL" is a common statement in the pedagogical modelling studies, proving the point (Maslova, 2014, p. 309). We assumed that nurturing LFHL in students goes far beyond fostering patriotism; it is a quintessence of patriotic education.

The study has been performed at the DPE and test sites (schools) of SSUSSE for three years (academic years 2018—2020). Samara Region is a unique district of the Russian Federation; it was namely the second capital of the Soviet Union in World War II. It is a cradle of the space achievements of Russia. The Russians, the Tatars, the Mordovans, the Chuvash have lived in Samara Region for many centuries. Thus, it is a multiethnic region. Samara has incorporated the heritage of these ethnic cultures. The specificities of the regional constituent were taken into account while creating the teaching model of nurturing LFHL at a pedagogical university and applying the findings of pedagogical modelling as a tool of upbringing. The keywords of Kuzmina's test tools (2015) were adjusted. The following keywords were put forth: Zhiguli legends and true stories, Volga land, famous people of Samara Region (Peter Alabin, Mikhail Chelyshev, Grigory Zasekin, Ilya Repin, Alexander Shiryayevets, Eldar Ryazanov, to name a few).

Modern educational technologies are significant in pedagogical modelling with RP-technology (Kozyreva, 2007), production of stimulation models (Casañ, 2017), the methodology of modelling the definitions related to upbringing (Skvortsova, Sushentseva, & Kozyreva, 2012), and designing the study set of constituents and criteria (Cheltsov, 2016) among them.

Results

The model called "Nurturing LFHL at the DPE of SSUSSE" is rested on qualitative analysis of specialized literature related to the study topic and the working experience of DPE professors. The model included the following elements: methodological foundation, goal-setting, content, and technology.

The methodological foundation comprises the statements of famous people on LFHL (Aleksandr Barkov, Yuri Efremov, Dmitry Likhachov, Konstantin Paustovsky, to name a few), the idea of the significance of pedagogical axiology in the educational process, the idea of the priority of patriotic upbringing at any level of education. The methodological principle of constructing the model is the following: patriotic upbringing requires predominance of LFHL as a quintessence of love for the home country and the best way to conceive the great sense via fine details.

Goal-setting of this model includes a goal and objectives of nurturing LFHL in students, formulating the strategy and tactics of achieving them. The goal of students' pedagogical upbringing is to shape "a positive emotional and value-based attitude" (Maslova, 2014) to the homeland via ideological values of the student's personality as a subject of educational settings. The objectives of nurturing LFHL in the students of a pedagogical university are raising awareness of ideological values and mitigating the adverse effects of globalization on fostering the student's personal traits.

The model's content allows for substantiation of the mode of operation and the existing system of nurturing LFHL at a pedagogical university. It is based on such design areas of work with the students as exploring the history of Samara Region, the traditions of this multiethnic region, its folklore, nature (the Zhigulevsky Reserve and the Samara Luka National Park), works of the poets and writers who lived in Samara Region, the pieces by the artists who have glorified the beauty of the Volga Region, their selfless devotion to research; pedagogical encouragement of the students who participate in nurturing LFHL and act as subjects of the activity aimed at enlightening the parents of primary school children studying at the SSUSSE basic sites; arranging collaboration of a university, a school, and out-of-school institutions of Samara Region designated to enhance the national and cultural identity of the students. The content of the design model of LFHL nurturing includes classroom-based and out-of-class educational activities, different working formats: discussions and national rituals (ethnic festivals of the Volga Region).

The model includes modern forms of upbringing: handling the website of Samara Linguistic School Virtual Museum. Elena Ivanyan, an SSUSSE professor, is the museum director. The model is also formed by a contest of theme student videos, e.g. "Samara is my homeland. At the root of ontolinguistics". Elena Ivanyan is responsible for organizing the project. Also, the model allows for conducting an annual regional interuniversity scientific linguistic student contest under the leadership of the DPE and "The Laboratory of Linguistic Senses" headed by professor Elena Ivanyan and associate professor Irina Gurova and for organizing pedagogical studies on nurturing LFHL in DPE students in the course of research and training work.

The constituent of the Technology design model includes arranging project and research activities of the students aimed at LFHL nurturing and based on the RP-technology; analyzing the situations reflecting LFHL moral values (a case method); glossing the LFHL notion; a pedagogical approach to the concepts of moral development; working with the evolution map of future teachers' value-based competencies. This constituent determines the structure of educational classes using the World cafe method. The students face a research task. They create stimulation models of LFHL nurturing at primary school encompassing all the participants of the educational process, the specificities of the Samara Region. Let us denominate it as Model 1.

Model 2 was created in this study based on the set of stimulation models of LFHL nurturing, which students produce during active and passive teaching internships at SSUSSE basic schools. This model designated for LFHL nurturing at primary school takes into account the opportunities of the 21st century.

The study shows that Model 2 and Model 1 have identical constituents, which was confirmed by the criteria of forging LFHL (Cheltsov, 2016). Model 1 had emotional and value-based, cognitive, and creative criteria. Model 2 had emotional, value-based, cognitive, and behavioural criteria. Third-graders were engaged to in the experiment. The models differ by the last criteria because it is primarily reflected in the behaviour of primary school children. A systemically important indicator of the pedagogical model is mastering patriotic patterns in various kinds of activities (Maslova, 2014).

As for the constituents of Model 1 and Model 2, the constituent "methodological foundation" has similar content. The constituent "goal-setting" of Model 2 does not include adverse mitigation effects of globalization on fostering the student's personal traits in the list of the tasks because no ninth- and tenth-graders view their homeland negatively.

The models differ by the constituent "content" in classroom-based and out-of-class educational activities (Model 1), working formats (extracurricular activities in Model 1), modern forms of upbringing: working with the Virtual Museum, a regional linguistic contest, theme video-making in Model 1. A considerable number of matchings in this constituent, on the whole, is also worth mentioning. The matchings include working at SSUSSE Zoological Museum and the exhibits of the Museum of the Department of Mathematics, Physics, and IT, visits to regional museums, to name a few. The technological constituent in Model 1 is characterized by diversity and intensity. It is associated with different educational backgrounds, age potential, and several limitations of young teachers during teaching internships at school, cf. (Musa & Musa, 2017).

The findings of the study were tested during a pedagogical experiment. The experiment's goal is to test the effectiveness of the design models for LFHL nurturing in students and primary school children. The DPE of SSUSSE and municipal budgetary educational institutions, such as School 94.

Control and experimental student groups of the DPE of SSUSSE and control and experimental student groups of primary schools were selected as an experimental site. In 2019, two control and experimental groups were selected at each school. The experiment was carried out in three stages.

1. The baseline stage of the experiment enabled us to preliminarily test the level of LFHL maturity in students and primary school children.
2. The constructing stage of the experiment implied using design models of LFHL nurturing while training the students, who are future teachers, and primary school children.
3. The control stage of the experiment included the second test of LFHL maturity in students and primary school children using the methods of the baseline experiment stage.

Criteria of LFHL maturity in Model 1:

- emotional and value-based criterion (personal attitude to the homeland, appreciation for the history of Samara Region, value-based competencies as personal traits, professional and moral values, commitment to environment protection, readiness to fulfil the civic duty and constitutional responsibilities aimed at defending the homeland and the home country);
- cognitive criterion (knowledge of the history, culture, and traditions of Samara Region as a multiethnic region, its cultural heritage, patterns of development of the society, substantiation of spiritual and moral priorities, the nature of Samara Region);

- creative criterion (engagement in volunteer and recreational, historical and cultural, charitable activities, commemorative events, search parties, to name a few; design of teaching aids on LFHL nurturing in primary schoolchildren).

Criteria of LFHL maturity in Model 2:

- emotional and value-based criterion (expressing compassion to the homeland, the cultural heritage, the nature of Samara Region; a positive vision of social and cultural values of multiethnic Samara Region);
- cognitive criterion (knowledge of the history, culture, and traditions of Samara Region as a multiethnic region, its cultural heritage, patterns of development of the society, substantiation of spiritual and moral priorities, the nature of Samara Region);
- behavioural criterion (caring for your nearest and dearest, supporting others, hands-on skills of children used for the improvement of Samara Region and also to each other, the school, the nearest and dearest).

The level of LFHL (high, average, or low) is determined by the completeness of LFHL levels depending on the criteria's qualitative and quantitative parameters. Each criterion has only positive manifestations of the characteristics. Positive manifestations of the criteria parameters are rare at the low level.

The findings of the constructing and control stages are represented in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Histogram reflecting the levels of LFHL maturity in the experimental student group (baseline and control stages).

The results analysis of the control stage of the experiment proved the level of LFHL maturity to have been increased in the experimental group of students. The analysis of the experiment's findings showed the increase of LFHL maturity level in the students of the experimental group with high and average levels of LFHL criteria prevail. Significant shifts are marked according to the creative criteria. LFHL has neither increased nor has increased insignificantly in the students of the control group, according to these criteria. The findings testify to the effectiveness of applying Model 1 in nurturing LFHL among the experimental group of students.

In order to assess the performance of Model 1, the study of using Model 2 in the educational process for primary school children was conducted. The experiment's construction stage showed that the level of LFHL maturity of primary schoolchildren in the experimental group had increased. High and average levels prevail, which is reflected in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Histogram reflecting the levels of LFHL maturity of an experimental group (baseline and control stages).

The data indicate the effectiveness of applying Model 2 for fostering LFHL in primary schoolchildren.

The level of LFHL maturity in primary schoolchildren of the experimental group has increased. High and average levels of LFHL criteria prevail. Nevertheless, the level of LFHL maturity has changed insignificantly in the students of the control group.

The robustness of the findings of the pedagogical experiment was tested using G-test. The statistical analysis results show a 95% probability of design Model 1 effectiveness for nurturing LFHL in students, whereas the design Model 1 is effective for nurturing LFHL in primary schoolchildren.

To assess the significance of changes in LFHL levels in the experimental group of students, the values at the baseline and control stages of the experiment were analyzed. Both positive and negative shifts were marked in the levels of LFHL maturity in the students. The students with a zero shift were excluded from the sample. Their level of LFHL maturity has not changed. The analytical sample size included 60 students. G observed is several atypical shifts. Atypical shifts are negative in the experimental group, whereas the number of shifts is 21. G critical is determined in the Table of critical values of G-test (Sidorenko, 2000) in the experimental student group:

$$G_{crit} = \begin{cases} G_{crit. 1} = 20, p = 0,01 \\ G_{crit. 2} = 23, p = 0,05 \end{cases}$$

We compare $G_{obs.}$ and $G_{crit.}$: if $G_{obs.} \leq G_{crit.}$, the differences in LFHL maturity in students are significant. Increasing the level of LFHL maturity in the students of the experimental group is significant. The error probability equals 5%.

A similar calculation for assessing the significance of changes in LFHL level was carried out for primary schoolchildren of experimental groups. $G_{obs.}$ that is a bunch of negative shifts equals 18.

$$G_{crit} = \begin{cases} G_{crit. 1} = 17, p = 0,01 \\ G_{crit. 2} = 19, p = 0,05 \end{cases}$$

Comparison of $G_{obs.}$ и $G_{crit.}$ showed that increasing the level of LFHL maturity in the primary school children of the experimental group is significant. The error probability is 5%. Therefore, the statistical analysis proved the effectiveness of the design models. Model 1 effectively nurtures LFHL in students; Model 2 effectively nurtures LFHL in primary schoolchildren with 95% probability.

Discussion

The study's findings showed that the statement about LFHL, which is not only a constituent but also a quintessence of patriotic upbringing in students, is correct. Focusing on the regional constituent in modelling and nurturing LFHL in the students of the pedagogical university yielded positive results.

Model 1, which was developed at the DPE and aimed at LFHL nurturing, is based on the mode of operation. It reflects essential links and properties of upbringing as a social phenomenon, fundamental aspects determining the vector of pedagogy and the study process of upbringing. Model 2 was created when the students arranged a series of simulation models on LFHL nurturing at primary school, taking into account the opportunities of the 21st century. Model 2 was facilitated because the managing actors nurturing LFHL in primary school children, such as mentors, interns, parents involved in upbringing, were engaged in group social dynamics (Musa & Musa, 2017). This indicates the need for the students to perceive their identities and present educational purposes. When Model 2 was applied, diffusion of value-based competencies was observed in the conscience of all the actors of the educational process. It was particularly confirmed by evolution maps of value-based competencies applied in the pedagogical experiment, among other test methods.

The findings of the pedagogical experiment testify to positive feedback in Model 1 and Model 2. It was found that arranging the system of nurturing LFHL in the students of the pedagogical university expedites nurturing LFHL in other actors of the educational process (primary schoolchildren taught by the DPE students in the course of an internship, parents of primary school children studying at the SSUSSE experimental sites. Consequently, being based on the mode of operation, Model 1 and Model 2 are recursive. They rest on self-excitation, which is a positive relationship. When the educational process is arranged this way, the teaching mentors of SSUSSE basic sites are included in feedback loops, enhancing the educational effect.

Therefore, the relationship between these models aimed at LFHL nurturing in students, future teachers, and primary schoolchildren is recursive and may be presented in the scheme below. Scheme 1 shows the emotional and value-based criteria; Scheme 2 represents cognitive criteria; Scheme 3 denotes a creative criterion; Scheme 3* designates a behavioural criterion in Model 2 designed for primary school children. It is reflected in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Recursive relationships in models of nurturing LFHL

The environment outside the educational institution also affects nurturing LFHL in both students and primary school children: parents, family members, friends, to name a few. However, interaction with a teacher is a directing vector of upbringing the students.

The results of LFHL nurturing at the DPE as a model of promoting primary school projects identified significant potential: an opportunity to enhance previous stages of education (Nain, Lipskaya, Karpova, & Nain, 2021); a need to make recreational and educational activities part of LFHL nurturing because these activities are associated with self-development and physical and moral recovery of any personality (Shamionov, Grigoryeva, & Grigoryev, 2019).

Conclusion

The study of LFHL nurturing at a pedagogical university has proven the efficacy of the actualization of the regional constituent. Being a professional and moral value, LFHL is becoming a quintessence of patriotism fostering in the current context of pedagogical work with students of different educational backgrounds. The study validity was confirmed by various test methods and a positive relationship between the models of nurturing LFHL at university and primary school.

The findings of the study can be used for designing and adjusting the curricula for future primary school teachers, elective and optional courses, for promoting the system of upbringing presented in the curricula of any pedagogical university, for designing the curricula of further education at pedagogical universities and professional development programmes for teachers implying personal, educational vouchers. Further research objectives are reflected in comparative pedagogical pursuits that consider the diffusion of LFHL nurturing at recently introduced study subjects: mother tongue (Russian) and literature reading in Russian as mother tongue along with other subject areas of education.

Abbreviations and acronyms

crit.	critical value
LFHL	Love for the Homeland
obs.	observed value
p	probability
DPE	Department of Primary Education
SSUSSE	Samara State University of Social Sciences and Education

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